

Strategies for managing risks in banks

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The Indian Economy is booming on the back of strong economic policies and a healthy regulatory regime. The effects of this are far-reaching and have the potential to ultimately achieve the high growth rates that the country is yearning for. The banking system lies at the nucleus of a country's development robust reforms are needed in India's case to fulfill that. It is now possible to market financial products and services on a global basis because of widespread use of internet banking have widened frontiers of global banking. In the coming years globalization would spread further on account of the likely opening up of financial services under WTO. India is one of the 104 signatories of Financial Services Agreement of 1997, thereby giving India's financial sector including banks an opportunity to expand their business on a quid pro quo basis.

Because of liberalization, deregulation and global integration of financial markets risk management activities will be more pronounced in future banking. This would be adding depth and dimension to the banking risks. As the risks are correlated, exposure to one risk may lead to another risk, therefore management of risks in a proactive, efficient & integrated manner will be the strength of the successful banks. It would be a mistake to conclude that the only way to succeed in banking is through ever-greater size and diversity. Indeed, better risk management may be the only truly necessary element of success in banking.

Research in common parlance refers to a search for knowledge. One can also define research as a scientific and systematic search for pertinent information on a specific topic. The

present study has been undertaken to examine the issues and challenges to be addressed by means of Risk Management in Banks.

The present paper aims to achieve the following objectives

- To highlight the various risks faced by banks;
- To present various methods and models for managing various risks seeing the present scenario and suggest suggestions to manage risk.
- To highlight the various challenges and strategies for managing risk in banks.

Area of study

The paper is not confined to any particular area; on the other hand it is applicable to whole India. However, opinion of officers/managers of various banks in Moradabad and Jaipur districts of Uttar Pradesh and Rajasthan respectively has been taken about the risk management in their banks. Their views have been incorporated in this paper. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on risk management in banks.

We have used qualitative research techniques as focus group discussion with respect to risk management in various banks. Our focus group discussion was based on some banks in region Moradabad and Jaipur districts. The discussions were based on key analysis of risk with emphasis on management of various types of risks.

Risk management [1-4]

Risk management is the analysis of risk coupled with the implementation of quality risk controls. Risk management is needed for banks and financial institutions, mainly because it insures a

margin of safety that guarantees a levered financial firm's solvency.

The capriciousness and innate risks associated with the financial markets makes it imperative for financial institutions and banks to implement risk management controls. The level of quality risk management policy and controls can make or break banks or financial institutions. Risk management is the process by which managers identify key risks, obtain consistent, understandable, operational risk measures, choosing which risks to reduce and which to increase and by what means, and establishing procedures to monitor the resulting risk position.

Risk Management is a discipline at the core of every financial institution and encompasses all the activities that affect its risk profile. It involves identification, measurement, monitoring and controlling risks to ensure that:

- The individuals who take or manage risks clearly understand it.
- The organization's risk exposure is within the limits established by Board of Directors.
- The expected payoffs compensate for the risks taken
- Risk taking decisions are in line with the business strategy and objectives set by Board of Directors.
- Risk taking decisions are explicit and clear.
- Sufficient capital as a buffer is available to take risk

The acceptance and management of financial risk is inherent to the business of banking and banks' roles as financial intermediaries. Risk management as commonly perceived does not mean minimizing risk; rather the goal of risk management is to optimize risk-reward trade-off. Notwithstanding the fact that

banks are in the business of taking risk, it should be recognized that an institution need not engage in business in a manner that unnecessarily imposes risk upon it nor should it absorb risk that can be transferred to other participants. Rather it should accept those risks that are uniquely part of the array of bank's services.

Risk management framework[5-8]

A risk management framework encompasses the scope of risks to be managed, the process/systems and procedures to manage risk and the roles and responsibilities of individuals involved in risk management. The framework should be comprehensive enough to capture all risks a bank is exposed to and have flexibility to accommodate any change in business activities.

An effective risk management framework includes:

- Clearly defined risk management policies and procedures covering risk identification, acceptance, measurement, monitoring, reporting and control.
- A well constituted organizational structure defining clearly roles and responsibilities of individuals involved in risk taking as well as managing it. Banks, in addition to risk management functions for various risk categories may institute a setup that supervises overall risk management at the bank. Such a setup could be in the form of a separate department or bank's Risk Management Committee could perform such function. The structure should be such that ensures effective monitoring and control over risks being taken. The individuals responsible for review function (Risk

review, internal audit, compliance etc) should be independent from risk taking units and report directly to board or senior management who are also not involved in risk taking.

- There should be an effective management information system that ensures flow of information from operational level to top management and a system to address any

exceptions observed. There should be an explicit procedure regarding measures to be taken to address such deviations.

- The framework should have a mechanism to ensure an ongoing review of systems, policies and procedures for risk management and procedure to adopt changes.

Figure-1: Risk Management Framework

Risk

Risk may be defined as reductions in firm value due to changes in the business environment. The major sources of value loss are identified as:

- Market risk: It is the change in net asset value due to changes in underlying economic factors such as interest rates, exchange rates and equity and commodity prices.
- Credit risk: It is the change in net asset value due to changes the perceived ability of counter parties to meet their contractual obligations.
- Operational risk: It results from costs incurred through mistakes made in carrying out transactions such as

settlement failures, regulatory requirements failures and untimely collections.

- Performance risk: It encompasses losses resulting from the failure to properly monitor employees or to use appropriate methods.

Strategies for managing risk

The strategies for managing various risks are mentioned herein below:

Managing market risk

Market Risk may be defined as the possibility of loss to bank caused by the changes in the market variables. It is the risk that the value of on-/off-balance sheet positions will be adversely affected by movements in equity and interest rate

markets, currency exchange rates and commodity prices. Market risk is the risk to the bank's earnings and capital due to changes in the market level of interest rates or prices of securities, foreign exchange and equities, as well as the volatilities, of those prices. Market Risk Management provides a comprehensive and dynamic frame work for measuring, monitoring and managing liquidity, interest rate, foreign exchange and equity as well as commodity price risk of a bank that needs to be closely integrated with the bank's business strategy. Scenario analysis and stress testing is yet another tool used to assess areas of potential problems in a given portfolio. Identification of future changes in economic conditions like – economic/industry overturns, market risk events, liquidity conditions etc that could have unfavourable effect on bank's portfolio is a condition precedent for carrying out stress testing. As the underlying assumption keep changing from time to time, output of the test should be reviewed periodically as market risk management system should be responsive and sensitive to the happenings in the market .

Likewise other risks, the concern for management of Market risk must start from the top management. Effective board and senior management oversight of the bank's overall market risk exposure is cornerstone of risk management process. For its part, the board of directors has following responsibilities.

- Mark out banks overall risk tolerance in relation to market risk.
- Ensure that adequate resources (technical as well as human) are devoted to market risk management

- Ensure that top management as well as individuals responsible for market risk management possess sound expertise and knowledge to accomplish the risk management function.
- Ensure that bank's overall market risk exposure is maintained at prudent levels and consistent with the available capital.
- Ensure that the bank implements sound fundamental principles that facilitate the identification, measurement, monitoring and control of market risk.

The first element of risk strategy is to determine the level of market risk the institution is prepared to assume. The risk appetite in relation to market risk should be assessed keeping in view the capital of the institution as well as exposure to other risks. Once the market risk appetite is determined, the institution should develop a strategy for market risk-taking in order to maximize returns while keeping exposure to market risk at or below the pre-determined level. While articulating market risk strategy the board needs to consider economic and market conditions, and the resulting effects on market risk; expertise available to profit in specific markets and their ability to identify, monitor and control the market risk in those markets; the institution's portfolio mix and diversification. Finally the market risk strategy should be periodically reviewed and effectively communicated to the relevant staff. There should be a Managing market risk process to identify any shifts from the approved market risk strategy and target markets, and to evaluate the resulting impact. The Board of Directors should periodically review the financial results

of the institution and, based on these results, determine if changes need to be made to the strategy.

While the board gives a strategic direction and goals, it is the responsibility of top management to transform those directions into procedural guidelines and policy document and ensure proper implementation of those policies. Accordingly, senior management is responsible to:

- Develop and implement procedures that translate business policy and strategic direction set by BOD into operating standards that are well understood by bank's personnel.
- Ensure adherence to the lines of authority and responsibility that board has established for measuring, managing, and reporting market risk.
- Oversee the implementation and maintenance of Management Information System that identify, measure, monitor, and control bank's market risk.
- Establish effective internal controls to monitor and control market risk.

Managing liquidity risk [8,9]

Bank Deposits generally have a much shorter contractual maturity than loans and liquidity management needs to provide a cushion to cover anticipated deposit withdrawals. Liquidity is the ability to efficiently accommodate deposit as also reduction in liabilities and to fund the loan growth and possible funding of the off-balance sheet claims. The cash flows are placed in different time buckets based on future likely behaviour of assets, liabilities and off-balance sheet items. Liquidity risk consists of Funding Risk, Time Risk & Call Risk.

- **Funding Risk:** It is the need to replace net out flows due to unanticipated withdrawal/nonrenewable of deposit
- **Time risk:** It is the need to compensate for non-receipt of expected inflows of funds, i.e. performing assets turning into nonperforming assets.
- **Call risk:** It happens on account of crystallization of contingent liabilities and inability to undertake profitable business opportunities when desired.

Liquidity risk is the potential for loss to an institution arising from either its inability to meet its obligations or to fund increases in assets as they fall due without incurring unacceptable cost or losses. Liquidity risk is considered a major risk for banks. It arises when the cushion provided by the liquid assets are not sufficient enough to meet its obligation. In such a situation banks often meet their liquidity requirements from market. However conditions of funding through market depend upon liquidity in the market and borrowing institution's liquidity. Accordingly an institution short of liquidity may have to undertake transaction at heavy cost resulting in a loss of earning or in worst case scenario the liquidity risk could result in bankruptcy of the institution if it is unable to undertake transaction even at current market prices.

Banks with large off-balance sheet exposures or the banks, which rely heavily on large corporate deposit, have relatively high level of liquidity risk. Further the banks experiencing a rapid growth in assets should have major concern for liquidity. Liquidity risk may not be seen in isolation, because financial risk are not mutually exclusive

and liquidity risk often triggered by consequence of these other financial risks such as credit risk, market risk etc. For instance, a bank increasing its credit risk through asset concentration etc may be increasing its liquidity risk as well. Similarly a large loan default or changes in interest rate can adversely impact a bank's liquidity position. Further if management misjudges the impact on liquidity of entering into a new business or product line, the bank's strategic risk would increase.

A liquidity risk management involves not only analyzing banks on and off-balance sheet positions to forecast future cash flows but also how the funding requirement would be met. The later involves identifying the funding market the bank has access, understanding the nature of those markets, evaluating banks current and future use of the market and monitor signs of confidence erosion.

The formality and sophistication of risk management processes established to manage liquidity risk should reflect the nature, size and complexity of an institution's activities. Sound liquidity risk management employed in measuring, monitoring and controlling liquidity risk is critical to the viability of any institution. Institutions should have a thorough understanding of the factors that could give rise to liquidity risk and put in place mitigating controls.

Liquidity risk strategy [9,10]

The liquidity risk strategy defined by board should enunciate specific policies on particular aspects of liquidity risk management, such as:

- **Composition of assets and liabilities.** The strategy should outline the mix of assets and liabilities to maintain liquidity.

Liquidity risk management and asset/liability management should be integrated to avoid steep costs associated with having to rapidly reconfigure the asset liability profile from maximum profitability to increased liquidity.

- **Diversification and stability of liabilities.** A funding concentration exists when a single decision or a single factor has the potential to result in a significant and sudden withdrawal of funds. Since such a situation could lead to an increased risk, the Board of Directors and senior management should specify guidance relating to funding sources and ensure that the bank have a diversified sources of funding day-to-day liquidity requirements. An institution would be more resilient to tight market liquidity conditions if its liabilities were derived from more stable sources. To comprehensively analyze the stability of liabilities/funding sources the bank need to identify:
 - a) Liabilities that would stay with the institution under any circumstances;
 - b) Liabilities that run-off gradually if problems arise;
 - c) That run-off immediately at the first sign of problems
- **Access to inter-bank market.** The inter-bank market can be important source of liquidity. However, the strategies should take into account the fact that in crisis situations access to inter bank market could be difficult as well as costly.

Managing credit risk [11]

Credit risk is described as the risk to have losses because counterparty is not capable to carry out its obligations

according to the terms of the agreement. Sometimes losses occur even when the counterparty does not breach the contract, but there are certain signs showing increasing probability of borrower's insolvency (e.g. downgrade in credit ratings of the borrower). Credit risk is one of the key risks for the banks as failure to properly evaluate it may lead to insolvency and bankruptcy. It is the overall responsibility of bank's Board to approve bank's credit risk strategy and significant policies relating to credit risk and its management which should be based on the bank's overall business strategy. To keep it current, the overall strategy has to be reviewed by the board, preferably annually. The responsibilities of the Board with regard to credit risk management shall, inter alia, include:

- Mark out bank's overall risk tolerance in relation to credit risk.
- Ensure that top management as well as individuals responsible for credit risk management possess sound expertise and knowledge to accomplish the risk management function;
- Ensure that the bank implements sound fundamental principles that facilitate the identification, measurement, monitoring and control of credit risk.
- Ensure that bank's overall credit risk exposure is maintained at prudent levels and consistent with the available capital
- Ensure that appropriate plans and procedures for credit risk management are in place.

The very first purpose of bank's credit strategy is to determine the risk appetite of the bank. Once it is determined the bank could develop a plan to optimize

return while keeping credit risk within predetermined limits. The bank's credit risk strategy thus should spell out:

- The institution's plan to grant credit, based on various client segments and products, economic sectors, geographical location, currency and maturity;
- Target market within each lending segment, preferred level of diversification/ concentration;
- Pricing strategy.

It is essential that banks give due consideration to their target market while devising credit risk strategy. The credit procedures should aim to obtain an in-depth understanding of the bank's clients, their credentials & their businesses in order to fully know their customers.

The strategy should provide continuity in approach and take into account cyclic aspect of country's economy and the resulting shifts in composition and quality of overall credit portfolio. While the strategy would be reviewed periodically and amended, as deemed necessary, it should be viable in long term and through various economic cycles.

The senior management of the bank should develop and establish credit policies and credit administration procedures as a part of overall credit risk management framework and get those approved from board. Such policies and procedures shall provide guidance to the staff on various types of lending including corporate, SME, consumer, agriculture, etc. At minimum the policy should include:

- Detailed and formalized credit evaluation/ appraisal process.

- Credit approval authority at various hierarchy levels including authority for approving exceptions.
- Risk identification, measurement, monitoring and control
- Credit origination and credit administration and loan documentation procedures
- Roles and responsibilities of units/staff involved in origination and management of credit.
 - Risk acceptance criteria

Managing interest rate risk

Interest rate risk arises when there is a mismatch between positions, which are subject to interest rate adjustment within a specified period. The bank's lending, funding and investment activities give rise to interest rate risk. The immediate impact of variation in interest rate is on bank's net interest income, while a long term impact is on bank's net worth since the economic value of bank's assets, liabilities and off-balance sheet exposures are affected. Consequently there are two common perspectives for the assessment of interest rate risk

- **Earning perspective:** In earning perspective, the focus of analysis is the impact of variation in interest rates on accrual or reported earnings. This is a traditional approach to interest rate risk assessment and obtained by measuring the changes in the Net Interest Income (NII) or Net Interest Margin (NIM) i.e. the difference between the total interest income and the total interest expense.
- **Economic value perspective:** It reflects the impact of fluctuation in the interest rates on economic value of a financial institution. Economic value of the bank can be viewed as the present value of future cash

flows. In this respect economic value is affected both by changes in future cash flows and discount rate used for determining present value. Economic value perspective considers the potential longer-term impact of interest rates on an institution.

Sources of interest rate risks:

Interest rate risk occurs due to

- Differences between the timing of rate changes and the timing of cash flows (re-pricing risk);
- Changing rate relationships among different yield curves effecting bank activities (basis risk);
- Changing rate relationships across the range of maturities (yield curve risk); and
- Interest-related options embedded in bank products (options risk).

Managing operational risk[12]

Banks and financial institutions are undergoing a sea change and today face an environment marked by growing consolidation, rising customer expectations, increasing regulatory quarymen's, proliferating financial engineering, uprising technological innovation and mounting competition. This has increased the probability of failure or mistakes from the operations point of view – resulting in increased focus on managing operational risks. Old perceptions and behaviors towards risk are changing. ORM is acquiring new credibility as a roadmap to add value to the business; and is garnering new attention from regulators and key stakeholders.

The discussions with the officers of various banks reveal that:

- Banks are reexamining their approach, culture and systems for managing operational risk.

- Banks continue to replace their first generation ORM systems - largely due to inflexible and rigid product design and the ongoing evolution of ORM methodologies.
- Average investment in ORM projects is increasing, as more and more banks are focusing on ORM's strategic business benefits
- Banks have begun investing in formal and sophisticated ORM systems.

There is a growing acknowledgement from banks that a consistent and effective operational risk management framework can help them achieve organizational objectives and superior performance. For example, by including a well-constructed operational risk process in the entire value chain, a bank can help ensure that the risks inherent in those activities are understood and addressed. In many instances an early involvement of operational risk management can increase the development speed of new initiatives.

The launch of the Basel II Capital Accord (the New Accord) by the Basel Committee for Banking Supervision, which requires banks to set aside regulatory capital for operational risk an important development that, has affected most financial services institutions worldwide. One of the major improvements in Basel II is that it ensures closer linkages between capital requirements and the ways banks manage their actual risk.

Challenges in managing risk

Increasing costs of compliance:

Development of an ORM model as part of a regulatory and economic capital framework is complex and takes time. There is a general agreement that the

major ORM challenge is increasing cost of compliance.

- **Efforts from the top:** Effective risk management program starts Top Management driven by the top management and adhered by the bottom line. However, if bank's top leaders perceive operational risk management solely as a regulatory mandate, rather than as an important means of enhancing competitiveness and performance, they may tend to be less supportive of such efforts.
- **Challenge of systematic Measurement of operational risk:** Many enterprises hold that their institutions are measuring operational risk. However, very few of them have been able to complete the Basel II quantification requirements, or yet to formalize the measurement process around the Basel II framework.
- **Access to appropriate information and reporting:** Effective management of operational risk requires diverse information from a variety of sources-including, for example, risk reports, risk and control profiles, operational risk incidents, key risk indicators, risk heat maps, and rules and definitions for regulatory capital and economic capital reporting.

By adopting an integrated operational risk framework, companies can ensure that all operational risks management initiatives are sustained and are aligned with the corporate strategy

Management framework

A vital operational risk management framework is made up of the following core components:

Figure-2: Framework for risk management

- The results of the risk assessment and quantification process enables management to compare the risks with its operational risk strategy and policies identify those risk exposures

that are unacceptable to the institution or are outside the institution's risk appetite, and select and prioritize appropriate mechanisms for mitigation.

Figure-3: Operational risk

Governance: Board of Directors defines key objectives for the bank and oversees progress towards achieving those objectives. It defines overall operational risk culture in organization, and sets the tone as to how a bank implements and executes its operational risk management strategy. Governance sets the precedence for Strategy, Structure and Execution.

- **Strategy:** A bank's strategy for operational risk drives the other components within the management framework and provides clear guidance on risk appetite or tolerance, policies, and processes for day-to-day risk management.
- **Structure:** It includes initiatives like laying down a hierarchical structure that leverages current risk processes, developing risk measurement models to assess regulatory and economic capital, and allocating economic capital vis-a-vis the actual risk confronted.
- **Execution:** Once operational risk management structure have been established by an organization adequate procedures should be designed and implemented to ensure execution of and

compliance with these policies at business line level. The first step includes identification and assessment of operational risk inherent in day-to-day processes of the bank. After assessment of inherent risk, target tolerance limit of risk should be established.

Basel's new capital accord [13-15]

Bankers' for International Settlement meet at Basel situated at Switzerland to address the common issues concerning bankers all over the world. The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision is a committee of banking supervisory authorities of G-10 countries and has been developing standards and establishment of a framework for bank supervision towards strengthening financial stability through out the world. In consultation with the supervisory authorities, authorities of a few non-G-10 countries including India, core principles for effective banking supervision in the form of minimum requirements to strengthen current supervisory regime, were mooted. The 1988 Capital Accord essentially provided only one option for measuring

the appropriate capital in relation to the risk-weighted assets of the financial institution. It focused on the total amount of bank capital so as to reduce the risk of bank solvency at the potential cost of bank's failure for the depositors. As an improvement on the above, the New Capital Accord was published in 2001, to be implemented by the financial year 2003-04. It provides spectrum of approaches for the measurement of credit, market and operational risks to determine the capital required. The spread and nature of the ownership structure is important as it impinges on the propensity to induct additional capital. While getting support from a large body of shareholders is a difficult proposition when the bank's performance is adverse, a smaller shareholder base constrains the ability of the bank to garner funds. Tier I capital is not owed to anyone and is available to cover possible unexpected losses. It has no maturity or repayment requirement, and is expected to remain a permanent component of the core capital of the counter party. While Basel standards currently require banks to have a capital adequacy ratio of 8% with Tier I not less than 4%, RBI has mandated the banks to maintain CAR of 9%. The maintenance of capital adequacy is like aiming at a moving target as the composition of risk-weighted assets gets changed every minute on account of fluctuation in the risk profile of a bank. Tier I capital is known as the core capital providing permanent and readily available support to the bank to meet the unexpected losses. In the recent past, owner of PSU banks, the government provided capital in good measure mainly to weaker banks. In doing so, the government was not acting as a prudent investor as return

on such capital was never a consideration. Further, capital infusion did not result in any cash flow to the receiver, as all the capital was required to be reinvested in government securities yielding low interest. Receipt of capital was just a book entry with the only advantage of interest income from the securities.

Suggestions

After going through the above study, we present the following suggestions based on the discussions with various officers of banks and financial institutions:

- Appropriate risk mitigation and internal controls procedures are established by the business units such that residual risk is mitigated to the acceptable level.
- Regular reviews must be carried out, to analyze the control environment and test the effectiveness of implemented controls, thereby ensuring business operations are conducted within acceptable risk limits.
- Top management ensures consistent monitoring and controlling of operational risk, and that risk information is received by the appropriate people, on a timely basis, in a form and format that will aid in the monitoring and control.
- In order to be effective, risk management policies must be clear and communicated down the line. Further any significant deviation/exception to these policies must be communicated to the top management/board and corrective measures should be taken. It is the responsibility of senior management to ensure effective implementation of these policies.
- An effective monitoring process is essential for adequately managing operational risk. Regular monitoring

activities can offer the advantage of quickly detecting and correcting deficiencies in the policies, processes and procedures for managing operational risk.

- There should be regular reporting of pertinent information to senior management and the board of directors that supports the proactive management of operational risk.

- Senior Management should establish a programme to:

1. Monitor assessment of the exposure to all types of operational risk faced by the institution;

2. Assess the quality and appropriateness of mitigating actions, including the extent to which identifiable risks can be transferred outside the institution; and

3. Ensure that adequate controls and systems are in place to identify and address problems before they become major concerns.

- Other suggestions:

1. Promote a strong culture of adhering to limits and managing risk exposure

2. Ongoing monitoring of positions and inherent risks

3. Combination of watchdog and trusted advisor

4. Understand how the business makes money and actively challenge initiatives if appropriate

Conclusion

Risk management underscores the fact that the survival of an organization depends heavily on its capabilities to anticipate and prepare for the change

rather than just waiting for the change and react to it. The objective of risk management is not to prohibit or prevent risk taking activity, but to ensure that the risks are consciously taken with full knowledge, clear purpose and understanding so that it can be measured and mitigated. It also prevents an institution from suffering unacceptable loss causing an institution to fail or materially damage its competitive position. Management need to evaluate the adequacy of counter measures, both in terms of their effectiveness in reducing the probability of a given risk, and of their effectiveness in reducing the impact should it occur. Where necessary, steps should be taken to design and implement cost-effective solutions to reduce the risk to an acceptable level. It is essential that ownership for these actions be assigned to ensure that they are initiated. Risk management and internal control procedures should be established by the business units, though guidance from the risk function may be required, to address particular risk. While the extent and nature of the controls adopted by each institution will be different, very often such measures encompass areas such as code of conduct, delegation of authority, segregation of duties, audit coverage, compliance, succession planning, mandatory leave, staff compensation, recruitment and training, dealing with customers, complaint handling, record keeping, MIS, physical controls, etc.

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